

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN LIGHTING CINEMATIC ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the modern significance of digital technologies in lighting cinematic environments. It explores innovative solutions for controlling light sources, simulations of lighting in virtual settings, and methods to enhance visual quality using digital tools. The article emphasizes the role of digital technologies in fostering creative and technical advancements in the film industry.*

Keywords: *lighting, visual expression, post-production, VFX, CGI, rapid, frame.*

In Uzbek cinematography, filming on tape continued until 2005, after which digital cameras gradually became widespread. Such technological changes were observed not only in Uzbek cinema but also in the global film industry.

In this regard, Marshall McLuhan, in his book *Understanding Media*, aptly states: "Technological innovations in the world of media keep evolving before they are fully assimilated" [1].

With modern technology and digital cameras, it became possible to monitor the entire filming process in real-time, allowing for immediate correction of any mistakes or shortcomings. The advancement of digital technologies has also enabled film editing to be performed using digital software, eliminating the need for tens of kilometers of film reels. These advancements allow limitless processing on special computers and modifications to every frame (exposure, color and tone, scale, editing) without negatively affecting the image quality.

Creating images using computer graphics has become easier compared to traditional painting techniques, making it possible to generate virtual environments that were previously unimaginable. The tools provided are so convenient that any flaws or imperfections can be easily corrected through software. Most computer programs are designed to facilitate the work of creators, allowing the final product to be adapted to various lighting conditions and quality requirements.

The modern film industry places great emphasis on the impact of lighting in visual expression to captivate audiences. This process is particularly executed through special computer technologies in virtual environments, namely VFX (Visual Effects) and CGI (Computer Generated Imagery). Although VFX and CGI are recognized as precise and well-defined technologies in the film industry, their application, influence in film production stages, and characteristics of visual effects have not yet been sufficiently studied from a scientific-theoretical perspective.

The application of VFX and CGI technologies requires various technical and technological approaches. As a result, the scientific community has not been able to fully research these processes in parallel with modern technological changes.

One of the main challenges in studying and evaluating VFX and CGI is that the methods used are evolving rapidly, making them obsolete quickly. Therefore, analyzing them based on independent and permanent criteria has become a complex task.

In Uzbek feature films, modern visual effects based on VFX and CGI technologies were first used in 1999 in Nozim Abbosov's film *Fellini*. Before that, traditional special effects—such as stunt effects, composite effects, mechanical effects, and optical effects—were primarily used to shape the visual representation of films.

Fellini entered history as the first experiment in Uzbek cinema to utilize computer graphics. The film integrated CGI-generated frames and digital visual effects with traditional techniques. It depicted the environmental degradation of the Aral Sea region, socio-economic issues, and the prevailing mood of despair in society. Scenes such as the film director (played by Bakhtiyor Zakirov) transforming into a mythical creature and a "ship of hope" emerging from a burning cinema screen would have been impossible to depict realistically using conventional filmmaking methods.

Regarding this process, the film's director, Nozim Abbosov, recalled: "I wrote the episode that was supposed to be shown in the film, but I could not imagine how to transfer it to the screen or the technology needed to execute it" [2].

In the film's finale, a cinema is shown catching fire. The projectionist, played by O. Shermukhammedov, stands in despair with tears in his eyes, witnessing the "ship of hope" sailing out of the burning screen. The ship gliding over the dried-up sea represents a symbolic-philosophical idea: art never burns or disappears, even in times of despair.

The visual effects used in the film were effectively employed as metaphors. One of the most complex effects and sequences in the movie is the scene where the ship flies over people. At that time, neither the technology nor the specialists capable of creating such an episode existed.

The main challenges in creating this effect lay in the fact that generating an artificial image in computer software was only half of the process, while integrating the virtual image with the real footage was the second, more complex stage. The difficulty of the work was evident in blending the artificial (raw) image with the real footage. Lighting, light direction, shadows, and environmental reflections were executed using software that was not yet fully advanced at that time.

Today, this episode may seem technically simpler, but in terms of execution, it still remains one of the most complex effects. Since the visual effects in the film were executed at a high level for its time, it was awarded the "Grand Prix" at an international festival held in Austria.

This film is considered one of the first in Uzbekistan and the entire Central Asian film industry to employ VFX technology. Traditional compositing studios could not create such high-quality and impactful episodes in a real setting. Additionally, when the film was shot, most experienced compositors had passed away, while younger specialists lacked the necessary knowledge and experience to handle such tasks. Therefore, a new approach to visual expression in the film was required – the episodes had to be created in a virtual environment using computer software.

At that time, creating images that could now be completed in a week required nearly six months. This process was a major challenge for the director – at some point, he even doubted whether the task could be accomplished with the desired quality. Additionally, transferring computer-generated images to film reels was one of the most difficult technical challenges faced by the creative team.

After the film *Fellini*, a practice began to emerge where VFX and CGI technologies were considered during the scriptwriting process, special sections were allocated for them, and effects were partially incorporated.

For example, in the movie *Alpomish* (dir. Hasan Fayziyev, cinematographer S. Mirzarakhimov, 2000), the scene where Alpomish shoots an arrow with his bow was specifically written to employ VFX and CGI. The flight of the arrow and its impact on the mountain, causing it to shatter, were created using digital graphics. However, this virtual arrow stands out from the real footage in terms of lighting – it appears overly bright, making it look artificial to the audience.

Digital cameras allow for more takes compared to film cameras. While film cameras can capture at most 12 minutes of footage per reel, digital cameras can continuously record more than 40 minutes of video. This, first and foremost, gives actors more freedom and confidence in front of the camera. Additionally, it allows directors to shoot the necessary takes without restrictions, carefully shaping exposure and composition. However, such flexibility can have a negative impact on the discipline and responsibility of the film crew. When working with film, the limited resources of the camera required high preparation for each take, and the crew had to adhere to strict discipline. Since digital technology has simplified this process, in some cases, a decline in creative discipline has been observed.

Another advantage of modern technology is that the widespread use of special effects in cinematography has enabled new interpretations of visual expression in films. Previously, cinematographers and artists used physiological impact techniques by filming models at various scales step by step. To create special effects using mechanical methods, film reels shot with actors and those containing effects were combined using an optical scanner.

However, this method led to a slight decrease in image quality. James Cameron commented on this issue: *"Nowadays, filmmaking technology advances to a new level every two years. This requires directors, cinematographers, and artists to skillfully utilize the integration of technology and art to create a new cinematic aesthetic."* [3]

The discussion of the global and U.S. film industries naturally increases interest in Uzbekistan's position in this field. To understand the impact of modern technology on the visual expression of Uzbek feature films, the methods of using them, and the technical and creative capabilities of CGI specialists, it is appropriate to refer to the insights of Lazizkhon Ganiev, head of *United Soft Media*, a studio recognized in the global media market and a specialist in CGI:

"Filmmakers consider CGI implementation for certain episodes already during the scriptwriting process. However, in some cases, CGI-generated scenes stand out from the overall composition of the film and are criticized for poor quality. There are several reasons for this."

After the script is approved, changes made during production, financial constraints affecting CGI work, the cinematographer and artist not being fully informed about episodes that need to be created in a virtual environment, shifts in the work schedule, and other organizational issues can all impact the process. Any studio working in the VFX and CGI field operates based on a precise mechanism and plan. No new elements are added or changed after the approved plan – this is one of the fundamental rules of VFX production. If the CGI process is meticulously planned according to the "VFX pipeline," the results will be both high-quality and purposeful. [4]

Characters created through VFX and CGI have the potential to be extraordinarily energetic and powerful. Previously, real individuals influenced the on-screen persona, but now, screen characters increasingly influence real-life individuals. An example of this can be seen in the films

Sevginator (Parts 1 and 2) by Abduvohid Ganiev, where the robotic bride character (played by Manzura Yuldasheva) serves as a striking example.

The use of VFX and CGI in films plays a crucial role in shaping environments and events that match the genre. For instance, in the sci-fi genre, real-life physics and laws are often defied. No matter how unnatural events may appear, if they are logically structured, the audience will accept them.

Although the *Sevginator* film was presented as a high-tech production, it did not feature a fully virtual character created through VFX and CGI. The robotic bride's movements were primarily conveyed through the actress's performance and filming in a specially lit capsule. Manzura Yuldasheva's robotic-like movements were displayed within a limited amplitude, but rather than her actions confirming that she was a real robot, it was the sharp speech of on-screen narrator Dildora Rustamova that established this perception.

The main CGI effects used in the film include:

- The levitating pointer stick in the classroom
- The robotic bride's collision with a bus after rescuing a girl
- Fast-motion scenes in the store
- The artificial shedding of tears

In the second part of the film, VFX and CGI are mainly observed in facial transformations and the slightly unnatural movements of the robotic bride. For instance:

- The robotic bride's face splitting into two
- Identical-looking nurses walking in the hospital
- Schematic displays appearing on-screen with time-lapse (zeitraffer) footage

At first glance, these elements may seem like visual effects, but in reality, they are editing-based effects rather than CGI-created sequences. This distinguishes them from CGI-generated frames in a virtual environment, as they are achieved by processing pre-recorded footage.

If computer technology and special effects are misused, they can negatively impact the essence of a film. Such shortcomings do not stem from technology itself but rather from filmmakers' improper application of effects.

Director Dilmurod Masaidov's film *Geolog* incorporated VFX and CGI technology as part of the scriptwriting process. One of the most notable features of the film is the use of rapid motion shots and the movement of animals.

Rapid motion is described by V. Pudovkin as "watching time through a magnifying glass." [5] It is a technique that captures high-speed movements in slow motion. In the past, during composite filming, frames were recorded onto film at a rate two to three times faster than the standard 24 frames per second, which, when played back, produced a slow-motion effect. This technique, for example, allows the audience to see the complete flight path of a bullet fired from a hunter's rifle.

Through this method, the director achieves a more impactful and profound delivery of the event's progression to the audience. In the opening scenes of the film, the image of a flying bullet remains in the viewer's mind throughout the storyline. Previously, rapid motion was used to depict large-scale objects such as galloping horses, explosions, and ocean waves—events that could still be perceived by the human eye. Such visuals require a significantly increased light source; otherwise, insufficient light reaches the film, causing the image to darken.

Although the special effects in the film were planned in the script, their execution was not entirely successful. For example, the scenes of the tiger attacking were created using VFX and CGI, but they did not blend seamlessly into the realistic setting. As the tiger attacks the bear in the chase scene, its movements lack boldness and aggression, failing to create suspense. The tiger was not specially designed for the film; instead, a circus animal was filmed and inserted into the movie. Its movement does not align with the storyline in terms of exposition and editing, and its appearance is far from the fierce and wild nature expected in such a setting. The tiger's injury and eventual death are only conveyed through Adiz Rajabov's gaze and the blood splattering onto the hunter (Dilmurod Masaidov)'s face. As a result, the audience does not fully experience the event's emotional impact.

In director Dilmurod Masaidov's historical-social film *Qo'qon Shamoli*, released in 2019 on national screens, the CGI-created wolf appears much more realistic.

Compared to the animals in *Geolog*, the wolf in this film is more precisely and qualitatively rendered. Its movements, appearance, and integration into the environment align fully with the demands of the storyline.

Although the scene where the wolf attacks the old woman is not explicitly shown, all the necessary shots and movements for editing have been accurately depicted. The required dynamics are maintained so that the audience perceives the wolf's aggression and frightening nature at the right moment. In contrast, *Geolog* lacks such visually impactful scenes. While visual effects should play a key role in forming the film's expressive function, they are used sparingly here.

Director Sarvar Karimov adapted Khudoyberdi To'xtaboyev's novel *Sariq Devni Minib* into the films *Sariq Devni Minib* and *Sehri Qalpokcha*.

In *Sehri Qalpokcha*, the history of the magical cap and ancient events are narrated. The cap has the ability to speak, and the person wearing it becomes invisible to others. The film revolves around Hashimjon and his magical cap. Transforming inanimate objects into speaking entities with human-like characteristics is a common fairytale element. Additionally, the cap serves as a tool for altering the speed of events, either accelerating or slowing them down.

The film's magical world and lighting solutions are executed at a high level. Natural lighting is used for daytime scenes, while night scenes are illuminated using the moon and fire sources. Objects such as a floating spoon, tea in a jar, a nail in a basement, and others were created using VFX and CGI. Their dynamic movement adds liveliness to the storyline and enhances the audience's belief in the film's world.

In *Sariq Devni Minib*, the comic book genre technique is extensively utilized as a form of visual expression. This method presents events through illustrated comic-style visuals, making the storyline more comprehensible. For instance, in Hashimjon's dream, the moment he bangs his friend's head against metal is depicted more effectively through a comic-style sequence rather than a realistic depiction, which is why this approach was chosen.

If the snake-fighting episode in the film had been shot realistically, it would have been significantly more complex and time-consuming compared to using VFX and CGI. Although VFX and CGI were used sparingly in both films, they were applied effectively and impactfully by the director. For example, the arrow shot at the squirrel, the vegetables flying into the basket, the illusionary scenes at the campsite, and the transformation of Hashimjon's moped were all accomplished using VFX and CGI.

While the visual effects in these films may appear simple, they enhance the credibility and dynamism of the visuals. The two films created by the production team are not blockbusters like *Harry Potter*, *The Chronicles of Narnia*, or *Spider-Man*, but they have their own place among young audiences. This is because works based on Uzbek literature are closer to the youth in shaping a national worldview.

In 2016, director Akbar Bekturdiyev filmed *Oykiz Ertagi*, a fairy tale film. It is the first fantasy film in the history of Uzbek cinema to use digital 4K and 5.1 surround sound technology. The film primarily aims to depict noble ideas such as patriotism and bravery. The story follows Princess Oykiz (played by Yulduz Rajabova), who, along with her friend Jonboz (played by Yigitali Mamajonov), searches for him and fights to free the country from invaders. The film makes extensive use of VFX and CGI. However, audiences familiar with the quality of Hollywood films' visual effects, virtual environments, and character design may find it difficult to fully accept the film's visuals.

Although the VFX and CGI elements were integrated into the film's overall aesthetic, certain shortcomings are noticeable. For example, in the opening shot, Sarang's kingdom appears relatively small in scale compared to the vast desert environment. In academic visual representation, colors should fade as perspective extends into the distance, but this effect is not sufficiently developed here. Additionally, issues with virtual camera movement are apparent. As the camera approaches the kingdom, its movement noticeably shifts, revealing poor execution of tracking motion in the virtual environment.

When analyzing the battle scene, it appears as if two suns are illuminating the sky because the shadows of the warriors fall in two different directions. In the crowd scenes, duplicated characters move in a symmetric pattern. However, VFX and CGI technology allow for independent movement of each character, meaning that each should have been assigned individual motion tasks in the computer software.

There are also errors in editing. For the battle scene to be visually comprehensible, the opposing forces should not cross in the same wide shot, yet here, the camera captures both sides from the same angle, which can disorient the audience regarding spatial orientation.

Most of the interior scenes in the film were created using VFX and CGI. This approach reduced creative constraints, saved time, and cut costs. The set design, lighting, costumes, and objects were executed based on storyboards developed in collaboration with the director, production designer, and cinematographer. However, in certain backgrounds, illogical movements are noticeable. For instance, as Alper walks, the background wall shifts in sync with him.

The lighting solutions align well with the film's dramaturgical demands. For example, before the palace falls into enemy hands, the lighting is soft and stable, whereas darkness is used to intensify the sense of conflict. According to the conventions of the fantasy genre, objects serve as symbolic elements: the underground kingdom is depicted in dark tones, while the healer's dwelling on the high mountain is bathed in sunlight. This approach effectively emphasizes the contrast between positive and negative characters.

Conclusion

This article analyzed the artistic and aesthetic aspects of lighting and visual expression in Uzbek cinema during the independence period. The development of the film industry was divided into two phases: from the 1990s to the mid-2000s and from 2005 to the present. The first phase

was characterized by the combined use of film and digital technologies, while the second phase marked the complete transition to digital filmmaking, as film stock became obsolete.

The advantages of digital technologies became evident in the consistency of lighting, the expansion of the color range, the enhancement of contrast depth, and the acceleration of post-production processes. As a result, cinematographers began exploring new aesthetic solutions by integrating modern technologies with traditional lighting techniques.

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